

JOURNAL OF SOCIAL RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT

www.jsrd.org.pk
editor@jsrd.org.pk

MEDIATING ROLE OF PROACTIVE PERSONALITY IN LINKING ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION AND INTENTIONS

Nafid Khan¹ & Irfan Ullah Khan²

¹Department of Business Administration, Gomal University, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan

²Department of Public Administration, Gomal University Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan

KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Entrepreneurial Education, Alertness, Entrepreneurial Intentions	<p>The present research aimed to examine the entrepreneurship from different dimensions that have been considered as significant determining factors in managing the desired situations towards entrepreneurship development in different contexts. The entrepreneurship is measured as significant predictor toward desired social and economic developments that aimed toward the improvements in human lives. The present research examined the desired and leading outcomes through various determining factors in exploring the entrepreneurship over comprehensive manners. So, entrepreneurial education is used as predicting variable in determining entrepreneurial intentions as these intentions are vital in determining behaviors of entrepreneurs towards desired outcomes. Present study used proactive personality as the mediating variable in connecting entrepreneurial education and intentions to produce new information and to contribute existing knowledge about significance of the entrepreneurship toward desired positive social and economic changes in human lives from different dimensions. Results are significant and provide suitable guidelines to policy makers.</p> <p>2022 Journal of Social Research Development</p>
Corresponding Author	Nafid Khan
Email:	nafidkhan39@gmail.com
DOI	https://doi.org/10.53664/JSRD/03-01-2022-10-102-115

INTRODUCTION

The entrepreneurship is considered as leading phenomenon that provides diverse leaning and significant opportunities to potential entrepreneurs to maintain their financial standing in diverse situations to sustain their strong positions in contemporary environment wherein entrepreneurs need critical support from other to commence desirous opportunities (İspir, Elibol & Sönmez, 2019). The entrepreneurship thus helps individuals through the significant knowledge about idea generation and commencement from diverse perspectives to maintain and sustain their liabilities toward available opportunities (Mazzarol & Reboud, 2020). The

entrepreneurship education is therefore inspiring for entrepreneurship development that routes at diverse leading outcomes from the diverse dimensions that nurtures entrepreneur abilities toward desired environment (Lyu, Shepherd & Lee, 2021). The entrepreneurship is important for making individuals toward personal business opportunities. Entrepreneurship is vital in maintaining individual behavior toward generation of ideas from diverse dimensions to start their personal businesses to overwhelm situation over diverse available chances (Pidduck, Busenitz, Zhang & Moulick, 2020). The entrepreneurship intentions are measured as originating phenomenon that inspires students those who enters practical careers from their academic career.

The literature revealed that entrepreneurship is emerging trend that inspires the students to directly involve in leading and available opportunities to maintain financial standings in competitive environment (İspir, Elibol & Sönmez, 2019). This trend has continuously gained the momentum from different perspectives to overwhelm situation and helps in sustaining environment toward desired liabilities to overwhelm situation as per the required demands (Lyu, Shepherd & Lee, 2021). Entrepreneurship is therefore persistent in providing different leading and available chances to entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship intentions in dependent upon education that helps in providing indulgent about entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial alertness helps in providing awareness and vigilance while passion denotes the desirability of the entrepreneurs to avail potential opportunities (Lina, Ionescu, Grigoriu, 2019). Also, entrepreneurial intention depends upon proactive personality of entrepreneurs that helps in understanding the intentions of individuals to use different traits to avail the available business opportunities in different situations (Gabriela, Alina, Maria & Daniel, 2020). Thus, intentions inspire individuals toward potential opportunities in different situations based upon skills, potential, awareness and knowledge (Qadasi & Nabil, 2021), to avail available possibilities of self-employment in the diverse circumstances to understand the nature and characteristics of entrepreneurship.

The entrepreneurship intentions are get developed through entrepreneurship education and alertness that helps in sustaining the environment of trust and motivation of different available opportunities from the different dimensions to maintain and sustain the required capabilities and abilities toward provision of various desired outcomes (Archana & Kumari, 2018). The entrepreneurship education through the entrepreneurship passion is significant is significant in developing entrepreneurs' intentions toward the available opportunities for starting their own businesses in diverse sphered based on own interests (Sesen, & Ekemen, 2020). The entrepreneurship alertness through proactive personality is important toward entrepreneurship intentions in developing positive consequences from diverse angles to maintain as well as sustain their standing in diverse situations (Wach & Bilan, 2021). Thus, entrepreneurship is vital in maintain desired environment through available opportunities (Fragoso, Junior & Xavier, 2020). The entrepreneurship is important in nurturing behaviors that how to sustain consistencies in attitudes towards availing opportunities to commence

personal businesses (Naz, Li, Zaman, & Rafiq, 2020). Entrepreneurs are required to inspire towards various outcomes and thus required to maintain desired and leading outcome from different dimensions.

Objectives of Study

1. To examine association between entrepreneurial education, proactive personality and entrepreneurship intentions (in-line with H1).
2. To examine mediating role of proactive personality in linking the entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intentions (in-line with H2).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The entrepreneurship is an emergent phenomenon that gained continuous momentum due to its role in providing ideas for commencing the personal businesses for generating the financial gains and providing the professional opportunities to others to become part of different leading businesses in different sphere of lives (Abimbola & Agboola, 2011). The application and understanding of entrepreneurship started through lens of economic development that appeared as outcome of the diverse leading opportunities designed for maintaining financial outcomes in diverse outlooks (Aparicio, Urbano & Audretsch, 2016). Entrepreneurship is known as starting the business on the small and medium level thereby engaging individuals to generate their financial outcomes best interests of their financial position establishment (Audretsch, Boente & Tamvada, 2007). The term therefore gained proper attention during the last decades due to the financial crunches and unemployment around the globe that provide inspiration towards entrepreneurship (Sesen, & Ekemen, 2020). The present study is an effort to examine role of entrepreneurship education toward entrepreneurial intentions. In this linking, this study aimed to examine the mediating role of proactive personality in connecting the entrepreneurial education, and entrepreneurial intentions.

Entrepreneurial Education

The entrepreneurship education is important that provides important knowledge about vitality of entrepreneurship to potential entrepreneurs those who aims to establish their own businesses in particular context thereby investing their capitals in different available opportunities to secure and expand their economic wealth through effective contributions toward financial development (Neck, & Greene, 2011). The entrepreneurship education is significant to develop entrepreneurship culture in diverse contexts to maintain and sustain desirability toward leading circumstances in attaining the anticipated and leading objectives (Rideout, & Gray, 2013). Entrepreneurship offers risk-taking opportunities to entrepreneurs to sustain their potentials over relevant knowledge and experience to maintain and sustain leading priorities to overwhelm the situation through nurturing behaviors (Ahmad, Rehman, Ali, Khan & Khan, 2014), to gain the required financial gains to produce more wealth. The entrepreneurship education is importance for building the desirability toward maintaining

environment of trust and commitment (Okoro, & Ezeonwumelu, 2019), that are critical in determining entrepreneurs' behavior leading to critical outcomes from diverse perspectives overcome at required potential for financial intimidation and outcomes (Azis, Haeruddin, & Azis, 2018). The education provides leading chances to young generation who enters into professional careers to maintain competitive edge in diverse situation and contexts for particular purposes.

Proactive Personality

The personality is important phenomenon that is judged through attitude and behavior of individuals which further overwhelmed at consistent temper towards proactive behavior (Bateman & Crant, 1993). The phenomenon of proactive personality discriminates individuals on basis of decision ability and power regarding changing environment (Claes, Beheydt & Lemmens, 2005). The proactive personality is an amalgamation of behavioral patterns that is inherent inclination and temperament toward the desired achievements (Bakker, Tims & Derks, 2012). The proactive personality is related with individuals' strength and direction in decision making that is mainly influenced through internal and external factors that further influence particular environment (Rui, Wang, Zhang & Peng, 2018). Proactive personality has significant influence on entrepreneurship intention as it helps in facilitating entrepreneurs to take appropriate decisions toward available breaks (Naz, Cai, Zaman & Muhammad, 2020) that are farther dependent on intellectual and circumstantial limits and parameters. The entrepreneurial intentions and proactive personality have direct relation in particular context based on attributes toward anticipated outcomes. The personality with learning and motivation is important for potential entrepreneurs to attain desired consequences from entrepreneurial chances as it inspires entrepreneurs that how to handle different activities in uncertain situation.

Entrepreneurial Intentions

The entrepreneurial intentions are important for nurturing the entrepreneurs' attitude and behaviors toward different entrepreneurial opportunities that are developed for positive consequences about role of diverse causes that are critical in sustaining the environment to desired success from different perspectives (Omari, & Alganbousi, 2020). Entrepreneurial intentions are developed when the potential and leading situational demands that inspires entrepreneurs to maintain leading goal-oriented as well as supply and demands analysis confirms the sustainability towards available opportunities that are critical in maintaining the environment and sustaining the desired outcomes (Arora, & Jain, 2019). These factors are thus considered as leading characteristics associated with entrepreneurial intentions to maintain the desirability toward the desired consequences (Azis, Haeruddin, & Azis, 2018), overwhelms at desired consequences from diverse leading characteristics and outcomes. The entrepreneurial intentions involve the challenging situational constraints that need the education and knowledge for effective execution of various plans for the entrepreneurship success from different leading environmental constraints (Agustina, & Fauzia, 2021). These

resources are careful as critical features for development of the entrepreneurial intentions towards available business opportunities that are vital toward the required determination for required success.

Research Hypotheses

- H1: There is positive and significant association between the entrepreneurial education, proactive personality and entrepreneurial intentions.
- H2: The proactive personality significantly mediated connection between entrepreneurial education entrepreneurial intentions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The material and method denote research methodology offered by scholar for conducting research study in particular context. The research design has been considered as structure (planned) that helps in obtaining research questions' answers in the systematic manners to reach the desired conclusion. In this study, quantitative research design was adopted with cross sectional survey. The approach is significant component of research that describes manner over which population has to be accessed (Bryman & Bell, 2011), thus positivism philosophy and survey approach were used to conduct the study. The survey strategies are commonly used in quantitative research studies wherein first-hand data is collected from the sampling that representing the entire population towards the generalization purposes (Bryman & Cramer, 2013). Thus, the study population comprised the 1550 students from the business administration departments from higher education institutions of southern region, KP, Pakistan.

The students' selection is based on their knowledge and maturities as these students from business administration departments have sufficient knowledge about entrepreneurship and its overwhelming role in developing the social and financial standings of students in contemporary competitive situations. Consequently, over statistical formula, for sample size determination, 318 sample was selected through Yamani (1967) formula to conduct study. Hence, 318 questionnaires were distributed wherein 300 were recollected and thus used analysis. The well structure questionnaire (adapted from previous studies like, Phan, Wong & Wang, 2002, for entrepreneurial education, Linan & Chen, 2006, for the entrepreneurship intentions and Crant & Kraimer (1999), for proactive personality) was used to collect data and statistical procedures (association was examined over correlation, impact was examined through the regression and mediation were examined over mediation procedures), were used to analyze data and find possible answers toward hypotheses to make decisions and reach desired conclusion.

RESULTS OF STUDY

The results of this study as outcomes of statistical procedures with the aim to examine the research variables descriptions and their interrelationships have been present in this section

that further helps in providing understanding about results' outcomes in deciding about hypotheses and reaching conclusion in systematic manner. Results are supported through results of existing research.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Entrepreneurial Education	300	1.30	4.80	3.2470	.82812
Proactive Personality	300	1.60	4.60	3.5333	.61341
Entrepreneurial Intentions	300	1.80	4.60	3.5653	.61055
Valid N (listwise)	300				

H₁: There is positive and significant association between the entrepreneurial education, proactive personality and entrepreneurial intentions.

Table 2 Correlation Analysis

		ENE	PRP
Proactive Personality [PRP]	Pearson Correlation	.455**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	300	300
Entrepreneurial Intentions [ENI]	Pearson Correlation	.645**	.523**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Association between predictors (entrepreneurial education), mediator (proactive personality) and criterion (entrepreneurial intentions) have been examined through first hypothesis (H₁) by using the regression. The results provide significant information about the association among research variables likewise entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intentions (R = .645 & P = .000), entrepreneurial education and proactive personality (R = .455 & P = .000) and the proactive personality and entrepreneurial intentions (R = .523 & P = .000) to examine the strength and direction in association. Thus, correlation provides the significant information in deciding about existence of potential association concerning strength and direction between predicting, mediating and criterion variables of present study that helps in deciding about relationships among variables thereby providing the directions toward the regression procedure. Consequently, from these results, the first hypothesis (H₁) is thus accepted.

H₂: The proactive personality significantly mediated connection between entrepreneurial education entrepreneurial intentions.

Mediation First Step (a)

Table 3 Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.4546	.2067	.3525	59.4726	1.0000	298.0000	.0000

Table 4 Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.1122	.1665	12.6867	.0000	1.7846	2.4399
Entrepreneurial Education	.4073	.0528	7.7118	.0000	.3034	.5113

Predicting Variable: Entrepreneurial Education

Criterion Variable: Proactive Personality

Path-a provides information wherein entrepreneurial education was used as predicting variable while proactive personality was used as criterion variable. The results revealed that 21% variance in entrepreneurial proactive personality is due to entrepreneurial education. The coefficient regression revealed that entrepreneurial education has significant influence upon proactive personality ($\beta = .4073$ and $P = .0000$). Thus, first mediation step provides significant information in moving towards second mediation path to examine the situation about mediation in reaching decision about partial and full-mediation while considering and measuring all paths in the mediation procedures while reaching the desired decision about mediation.

Mediation Second & Third Steps (b & c)

Table 5 Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6942	.4820	.1943	139.1694	2.0000	297.0000	.0000

Table 6 Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.0879	.1503	7.2377	.0000	.7921	1.3837
Proactive Personality	.2654	.0494	5.3764	.0000	.1683	.3626
Entrepreneurial Education	.4217	.0400	10.5401	.0000	.3430	.5004

Predicting Variable: Entrepreneurial Education, Proactive Personality

Criterion Variable: Entrepreneurial Intentions

The path second and third provides the information about predictability of entrepreneurial intentions through entrepreneurial education and proactive personality. Results revealed 48% change in entrepreneurial intentions is due to entrepreneurial education and proactive personality in particular context. The results showed further that entrepreneurial education has significant influence upon intentions of entrepreneurs ($\beta = .4217$ and $P = .0000$) while significant impact proactive personality on the entrepreneurial intention ($\beta = .2654$ and $P = .0000$) through indirect relationship after inclusion of the proactive personality as mediator. Thus, the results provide significant information in moving to the fourth path and reaching the decision that whether the proactive personality shows partial of full mediating role in the mediation thereby considering the fourth step of mediation procedure toward desired conclusion.

Mediation Fourth Step (c)

Table 7 Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6446	.4156	.2185	228.7695	1.0000	298.0000	.0000

Table 8 Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.6485	.1193	13.8145	.0000	1.4137	1.8834
Entrepreneurial Education	.5298	.0350	15.1251	.0000	.4609	.5987

Predicting Variable: Entrepreneurial Education

Criterion Variable: Entrepreneurial Intentions

Table 9 Sobel Test (Normal Theory Test)

Effect	se	Z	p
.3444	.0247	4.3856	.0000

The fourth path of mediation provides information about predictability of entrepreneurial intentions through entrepreneurial alertness that shows 0742 variances in entrepreneurial intentions due to entrepreneurial education through direct relationship between research variables. The coefficient of regression further showed that entrepreneurial education has significant influence upon intentions of the entrepreneurs ($\beta = .5298$ and $P = .0000$). The mediation procedure provides significant data in reaching the mediation conclusion as the coefficient in direct relationship ($\beta = .5298$) has been thus reduced to ($\beta = .4217$), after the arrival of proactive personality as mediator while significant values remained same. Thus, the proactive personality partially mediated relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and intentions which has thus been confirmed through normal theory test wherein the

total effect (.3444) and significance value (.0000), that remained in the required threshold values for confirming the mediation. Thus, from results of mediation all paths, hypothesis (H5), is therefore accepted.

DISCUSSION

The entrepreneurship is recognized as significant phenomenon in determining financial success from different dimensions based upon the social, cultural and financial values that determines vital opportunities for development. Entrepreneurship in developing countries is effective due to its critical role in developing the skills and knowledge of entrepreneurs to avail the different chances for improving their standards and standings and to contribute their shares toward the financial development (Oosterbeek, Praag & Ijsselstein, 2010; Quinn & Woodruff, 2019). The entrepreneurship remained pivot around various developmental chances due to its critical role in provision of various chances that are vital in determining success and realization from different perspectives based on situations and circumstances that are vital for considering environment for different purposes (Littlewood & Holt, 2018; Lyu, Shepherd & Lee, 2021), aimed at improving the positive and leading development as desired from entrepreneurship. Proactive personality is vital towards entrepreneurship as it provides the proactivity, dedication and confidence towards different options desired for potential development.

The proactive individuals are required to put their strong emphasis upon utilization of skills and knowledge to maintain the desired situations in sustaining environmental stability and motivation towards desirable success through effective skills and knowledge management approaches (Costa, Wach, Caetano, & Santos, 2015; Hu, Wang, Zhang & Bin, 2018). The entrepreneurship is thus effective in maintaining the conducive environment for social and economic growth in diverse situations for attaining diverse outcome based on information and attributed for the effective personalities to maintain the desired consequences in the diverse situations (Botsaris, & Vamvaka, 2016; Duong, Le, & Ha, 2021). The skills and knowledge over learning and motivation are significant in sustaining environment of trust and confidence. Entrepreneurial education has significant connection with entrepreneurial passion as effective education provides information through effective knowledge towards the desired determinations in sustaining conducive environment of trust and commitment that are critical in sustaining environment toward desired outcomes leading toward desired development and success from diverse perspectives (Azis, Haeruddin, & Azis, 2018; Shah, Amjed, & Jaboob, 2020).

The entrepreneurship is vital for developing emotional strength of entrepreneurs to attain desired outcomes through application of various strategic approaches that are vital toward determination of desired outcomes based upon skills and knowledge through effective and vital application of the various strategic approaches (Buana, Hidayat, & Prayogi, 2017; Gabriela, Alina, Maria, & Daniel, 2020). The entrepreneurship is imperative for students to

overwhelm the situation and to maintain desirability towards leading outcomes through effective education. The entrepreneurial education, personality and intentions are effective in sustaining environment wherein entrepreneurs are required to put their strong efforts to avail the different available leading opportunities towards the application of different knowledge, techniques and approaches that are dynamic toward the determination of the required outcomes through effective and required capabilities and outcomes in the diverse situation to maintain anticipated consequences (Buana, Hidayat & Prayogi, 2017; Agustina, & Fauzia, 2021).

In this linking, the entrepreneurial education is vital for developing effective personalities thereby developing the learning and motivation which are important for developing the entrepreneurial intentions that are imperative for attaining the desired outcomes through effective utilization and knowledge and competencies (Lackéus, & Williams, 2015; Costa, Santos, Wach, & Caetano, 2018). The entrepreneurship is thus important for developing the social and financial contexts of entrepreneurs in different and leading situations. Thus, entrepreneurial intentions and passion have direct and significant connection and both are significant for nurturing positive behaviors leading towards the effective entrepreneurial intentions desired for the particular development and outcomes (Karimi, Biemans, Lans, & Mulder, 2016; Fragoso, Rocha, & Xavier, 2020). In this connection, the entrepreneurs are required to show their commitment and motivation through different leading practices to ensure desired potentials as required for nurturing desired intentions and attaining desired outcomes and success.

CONCLUSION

The present study provides significant information about the existence of relationships in particular context based on certain assumptions as developed from theoretical framework that have confirmed through different empirical findings and validated through the results of different previous studies to make clear position and offer new knowledge from diverse dimensions about the existing realities to contribute the knowledge. The entrepreneurship has been confirmed as most significant phenomenon through different dimensions that changes entire standings of potential entrepreneurs from the social, cultural and financial perspectives. Thus, conclusion helps in providing the information about decision making that abridges research outcomes for particular purpose in specific context to offer certain theoretical contributions over innovative methods and procedures that are expected to be used as guiding principles in further researches. Thus, following decisions are extracted from research. First hypothesis was about association between entrepreneurial education, personality and intention was confirmed over correlation. Second hypothesis was about mediating role of proactive personality to link education and entrepreneurial intentions by using the macro mediation procedure and results shown significant information about the partial mediation among research variables and thus based on these results, hypothesis was accepted.

Recommendations

1. The proactive personality is important for considering the different attributes that are critical in sustaining environment of trust and confidence and entrepreneurs are required to show their learning and motivation as composite of personality to attain desired outcomes from entrepreneurship.
2. The entrepreneurship is measured as major procedure to identify the opportunities, acquiring and understanding resources toward requirement, planning and realizing different tasks and thus entrepreneurs are required to put their strong emphasis upon the entire process of entrepreneurship.
3. The entrepreneurship education is required to be effectively imparted to students to aware them toward positive consequences hailing from entrepreneurship chances that are vital for developing social and financial contexts overwhelmed at desired and leading outcomes for success.
4. The careful selection of the research variables of different nature like independent, dependent and mediating variables from the existing literature and its conversion toward theoretical framework is primary contribution from where hypotheses were developed and tested in field study to extract desired information.

REFERENCES

- Abimbola, O. H., & Agboola, M. G. (2011). Environmental factors and entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 13(4), 166-176.
- Agustina, T. S., & Fauzia, D. S. (2021). The Need for Achievement, Risk-Taking Propensity, And Entrepreneurial Intention of The Generation Z. *Risenologi*, 6(1), 96-106.
- Ahmad, I., Rehman, K., Ali, A., Khan, I., & Khan, F. A. (2014). Critical Analysis of the Problems of Education in Pakistan: *Possible Solutions*, 3(2), 79-84.
- Aparicio, S., Urbano, D., & Audretsch, D. (2016). Institutional factors, opportunity entrepreneurship and economic growth: Panel data evidence. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 102, 45-61.
- Archana, R. V., & Kumari, K. (2018). A Study on Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Entrepreneurship Intention. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* 119 (12), 14839-14851.
- Arora, S., & Jain, S. (2019). Influence of Gender on Entrepreneurial Intentions among Business Management Students. *Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 54(3).
- Audretsch, D. B., Boente, W., & Tamvada, J. P. (2007). Religion and entrepreneurship. *Jena Economic Research Paper*, (2007-075).
- Azis, M., Haeruddin, M. I. M., & Azis, F. (2018). Entrepreneurship education and career intention: The perks of being a woman student. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 21(1), 1-10.
- Bakker, A. B., Tims, M., & Derks, D. (2012). Proactive personality and job performance: The role of job crafting and work engagement. *Human relations*, 65(10), 1359-1378.

- Bateman, T. S., & Crant, J. M. (1993). The proactive component of organizational behavior: A measure and correlates. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 14, 103-118.
- Botsaris, C., & Vamvaka, V. (2016). Attitude toward entrepreneurship: structure, prediction from behavioral beliefs, and relation to entrepreneurial intention. *Journal of Knowledge Economy*, 7(2), 433-460.
- Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2011). *The Business research methodologies*. Oxford: The Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A., & Cramer, D. (2013). *Quantitative data analysis with SPSS: A guide for social scientists*. New York, NY, US: Routledge.
- Buana, Y., Hidayat, D., & Prayogi, B. (2017). Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on Entrepreneurial Intention of University Students. *Business Review*, 8(1), 67-75.
- Claes, R., Beheydt, C., & Lemmens, B. (2005). One-dimensionality of abbreviated proactive personality scales across cultures. *Applied Psychology*, 54, 476-489.
- Costa, S. F., Santos, S. C., Wach, D., & Caetano, A. (2018). Recognizing opportunities across campus: Effects of cognitive training and entrepreneurial passion on business opportunity prototype. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 56(1), 51-75.
- Costa, S. F., Wach, D., Caetano, A., & Santos, S. C. (2015). The Effect of Cognitive Training and Entrepreneurial Passion on the Business Opportunity Prototype. In *Academy of Management Proceedings* (Vol. 2015, No. 1, p. 18186). Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510: Academy of Management.
- Crant, M. J., & Kraimer, L. (1999). The proactive personality scale as a predictor of entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 34(3), 42- 49.
- Duong, C. D., Le, T. L., & Ha, N. T. (2021). The Role of Trait Competitiveness and Entrepreneurial Alertness in the Cognitive Process of Entrepreneurship Among Students: A Cross-Cultural Comparative Study Between Vietnam and Poland. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 13(4), 25-42.
- Fragoso, R., Rocha-Junior, W., & Xavier, A. (2020). Determinant factors of entrepreneurial intention among university students in Brazil & Portugal. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 32(1), 33-57.
- Gabriela, B., Alina, M., Maria, B., & Daniel, B. (2020). Entrepreneurship Education through Successful Entrepreneurial Models in Higher Education Institutions. 12, 1267.
- İspir, Ö., Elibol, E., & Sönmez, B. (2019). The relationship of personality traits and entrepreneurship tendencies with career adaptability of nursing students. *Nurse education today*, 79, 41-47.
- Karimi, S., Biemans, H. J., Lans, T., Chizari, M., & Mulder, M. (2016). The impact of entrepreneurship education: A study of Iranian students' entrepreneurial intentions & opportunity identification. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 54(1), 187-209.
- Lackéus, M., & Williams Middleton, K. (2015). Venture creation programs: bridging entrepreneurship education and technology transfer. *Education+ training*, 57(1), 48-73.

- Lina, D., Ionescu, A., & Grigorut, M. (2019). The entrepreneurial orientation in Romanian Higher Education. In Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Education and New Learning Technologies, Palma, Spain, 1-3, 9864-9872.
- Linan, F., & Chen, Y. (2006). Testing the entrepreneurial intention model on a two-country sample. (Working paper) Documents de Treball. *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona*, Spain.
- Littlewood, D., & Holt, D. (2018). Social entrepreneurship in South Africa: Exploring the influence of environment. *Business & Society*, 57(3), 525-561.
- Lyu, J., Shepherd, D. M., & Lee, K. (2021). Teaching entrepreneurship in China: culture matters. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*.
- Mazzarol, T., & Reboud, S. (2020). The Entrepreneur. In Entrepreneurship and Innovation (pp. 35-61). Springer, Singapore.
- Naz, S., Li, C., Zaman, U., & Rafiq, M. (2020). Linking Proactive Personality and Entrepreneurial Intentions: A Serial Mediation Model Involving Broader and Specific Self-Efficacy. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), 166.
- Neck, H. M., & Greene, P. G. (2011). Entrepreneurship education: known worlds and new frontiers. *Journal of small business management*, 49(1), 55-70.
- Okoro, C., & Ezeonwumelu, V. U. (2019). Motivating students for entrepreneurial education in nigerian primary schools: The 'catching them young phenomenon'. *Equatorial Journal of Education and Curriculum Studies*, 3(1), 28-36.
- Omari, A., & Alganbousi, S. (2020). The entrepreneurial intentions among undergraduate students of Sultan Qaboos University and its relationship with their proactive personality. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*, 10(3), 37-48.
- Oosterbeek, H., M. van Praag, and A. Ijsselstein (2010). "The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on Entrepreneurship Skills and Motivation," *European Economic Review*, 54, 442-454.
- Phan, P. H., Wong, P., & Wang, C. K. (2002). Antecedents to Entrepreneurship among University Students in Singapore: Beliefs, Attitudes and Background. *Journal of Enterprising Culture*, 10, 151-174.
- Pidduck, R. J., Busenitz, L. W., Zhang, Y., & Moulick, A. G. (2020). Oh, the places you'll go: A schema theory perspective on cross-cultural experience and entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 14, e00189.
- Qadasi, A., & Nabil, A. (2021). Toward a Comprehensive Model on Entrepreneurial Intentions of University Students. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 9, 114-135.
- Quinn, S., & Woodruff, C. (2019). Experiments and entrepreneurship in developing countries. *Annual Review of Economics*, 11, 225-248.

- Rideout, E. C., & Gray, D. O. (2013). Does entrepreneurship education really work? A review and methodological critique of empirical literature on effects of university-based entrepreneurship education. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 51(3), 329-351.
- Rui, H., Wang, L., Zhang, W., & Peng, B. (2018). Creativity, Proactive Personality, and Entrepreneurial Intention: The Role of Entrepreneurial Alertness. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14.
- Sesen, H., & Ekemen, M. A. (2020). Data on personal and contextual factors of university students on their entrepreneurial intentions in some Turkish universities. *Data in Brief*, 28, 105086.
- Shah, I., Amjed, S., & Jaboob, S. (2020). The moderating role of entrepreneurship education in shaping entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Economic Structures*, 9 (19), 2-15.
- Wach, K., & Bilan, S. (2021). Public support and administration barriers towards entrepreneurial intentions of students in Poland. *Administrative Management Public*, (36), 67-80.